

SOCIO-ECONOMIC DETERMINANTS OF SELF-MEDICATION AMONG THE STUDENTS OF UNIVERSITY OF SWAT, PAKISTAN

Sadullah Khan^{*1}, Anwar Ali², Malak Abdul Jabbar Khan³, Hazrat Hussain⁴

^{*1,2,3,4}BS Sociology, Department of Social and Gender Studies, University of Swat

¹saadullahkhan15499@gamil.com, ²anwarsocio5@gmail.com, ³Malakjabbar123@gmail.com, ⁴knhussain007@gmail.com

Corresponding Author: *

Sadullah Khan

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17731340>

Received	Accepted	Published
05 October 2025	13 November 2025	27 November 2025

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between self-medication and demographic characteristics and poverty among University of Swat students in Pakistan. Self-medication, or taking medications without a prescription from a doctor, can have major negative impacts on one's health, including treatment failure, drug resistance, and adverse side effects. Stratified random sampling was used to choose a sample of 367 BS students, and binary logistic regression was used to evaluate the results. The findings indicate that the most important factor is poverty. Self-medication is 129% more common among students from high-poverty households ($p < 0.01$). Another factor is gender: male students are 88% more likely than female students to self-medicate ($p = 0.02$). Another important consideration is family structure. Self-medication is 67% more common among students from extended families and 42% more common among students from joint households ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, the likelihood of urban students self-medicating is 51% higher than that of rural students ($p = 0.06$). Other variables, including faculty, academic semester, and age, did not significantly affect the results. These results demonstrate how family dynamics and poverty have a significant impact on self-medication behaviors. The study highlights the significance of raising awareness and formulating plans to lower student self-medication, particularly among those who are struggling financially. By addressing these problems, students' health and wellbeing can be enhanced and the dangers of self-medication can be decreased.

Keywords: Self-medication, Poverty, Binary Logistics Regression, Demographics factors.

INTRODUCTION

Self-medication defined as the use of medicine and drugs without doctor's prescription or professional advice to treat symptom called self-medication (Hughes et al., 2019). This may entail treating illnesses or symptoms with antibiotics without a prescription or expert guidance (Morgan et al., 2011). The use of pharmaceuticals by consumers to treat illnesses or symptoms that they have identified on their own is also included in the category of self-medication. This includes the

intermittent or continuous use of prescribed drugs for long-term or recurrent ailments (WHO, 2000). In essence, self-medication happens when people decide to use over-the-counter medications to cure their ailments or symptoms, or when they decide to heed amateur advice (Shaghghi & Allahverdi, 2014).

One example is using over-the-counter medication to treat ailments that one a diagnosis (Gyawali et al., 2015). According to Shamsi and Bayati (2010),

drugs are chemical substances that are used or intend to be utilizing in the diagnosis, treatment, or prevention of disease. Self-medication refers to using pharmaceuticals by people without a prescription, doctor's advice, or supervision (Albarrán & Zapata, 2008). In self-medication, the patient, their caregiver, or guardian make decisions about which medication to take it for a particular disease without consulting a doctor (Pfaffenbach, Tourinho, & Bucarechi, 2010).

Human health risks associated with self-medication include treatment failure, drug resistance, and adverse pharmacological events, such as death (Pan et al., 2012). Negative effects include treatment failure, drug toxicity, and antibiotic resistance can arise from the improper use of drugs, such as antibiotics (Zeb et al., 2022). Self-medication can endanger human safety by increasing the risk of drug use, and drug dependence, and obscuring underlying medical issues. It can also lead to drug resistance and complicate diagnosis (Aljinović et al., 2015; Alshahrani et al., 2019). The most prevalent practice in developing nations is self-medication, which causes severe liver failure (arson AM, 2010). There are risks associated with self-medication, including mortality (Bennadi, 2013). According to Tesfamariam et al. (2019), self-medication (81.8%) is a dangerous practice for human health. One of the largest socio-health and economic issues in many societies is medication in general. medication interactions, misdiagnosis, coverage of diseases, elevated consequences, and antibiotic resistance (Limaye and others, 2017) Research indicates that a few variables that contribute to self-medication include not having enough time to see a doctor, thinking that drugs are safe, gathering and storing outdated prescriptions at home, having easy access to drugs, and being able to purchase drugs without a prescription. (Amani, Mohammadi, Shaker, & Shahbazzadegan, 2011; Alghanim, 2011) . The following medical consequences of self-medication include drug dependency, drug interactions, accidental poisoning, liver and renal disorders, reduced quality of life, bacterial resistance, hidden signs and symptoms of the underlying disease, delayed diagnosis, incomplete treatment (Amani et al., 2011; Ansari, Abshenas, Khanzadeh, & Masoudi,

2007; Mumtaz, Jahangeer, Mujtaba, Zafar, & Adnan, 2011; Sawalha, 2007). The primary goal of the research is to determine how demographics factors and poverty affect the use of self-medication while many factors contribute but this study focuses on poverty and demographics factors only. These variables were picking because they can have a major impact on University of Swat students' health-related behaviors, especially self-medication. By concentrating on these particular demographics factors and poverty the research provides a thorough understanding of how these factors influence this student population's propensity for self-medication. The University of Swat, which situated in Pakistan's Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province's district of Swat, is the subject of this study. With more than 9,000 students, the University of Swat is a well-known institution in the region that attracts students from all over the country. Research on the prevalence and reasons of self-medication among University of Swat students is lacking, despite its significance. This study focused on the factors that affect University of Swat students' use of self-medication to close this information gap, the purpose of this research is to advise the University of Swat strategies for enhancing student well-being and addressing the underlying impact of the demographics factors and poverty on self-medication by investigating self-medication in this setting.

Literature Review

Self-medication practices are significantly predicted by poverty. Due to financial limitations, people frequently choose over-the-counter drugs or alternative therapies over professional healthcare services. According to Borges et al. (2019), poverty is a stressor that drives people to self-medicate as an economical way to deal with health problems. In a similar vein, Ahmed et al. (2023) discovered that people in low-income groups turn to self-medication since they have less access to reasonably priced medical treatment. Research from developing nations, such as Pakistan and India, shows how common self-medication is among those with poor incomes. People with low incomes are far more likely to self-medicate, frequently taking antibiotics without a

prescription, according to Panda et al. (2017). This trend is made worse in places with inadequate healthcare systems, where poverty restricts access to medical care both financially and physically.

One of the main causes of self-medication is the expense of medical care. People are forced to rely on self-diagnosis and over-the-counter remedies due to high medical consultation costs, expensive treatments, and a lack of reasonably priced prescriptions. According to Green et al. (2021), poverty raises the likelihood of unfavorable health outcomes by influencing healthcare-seeking habits and resulting in incomplete treatment regimens.

The problem is made worse in Pakistan by the uncontrolled sale of pharmaceuticals. According to Malik and Bhattacharyya (2019), self-medication is encouraged by the easy access to over-the-counter medications in low-income areas, especially for those who cannot afford medical consultations. University students exhibit this dynamic, since they frequently deal with financial strains that make it difficult for them to prioritize paying for healthcare.

Around the world, areas with high rates of poverty are where self-medication is most common. According to Awad et al. (2005), impoverished communities in Sudan mainly rely on self-medication because prescribed medications and medical care are too expensive. Similarly, Selvaraj et al. (2014) discovered that those with lower incomes and educational levels were much more likely to self-medicate in metropolitan Pondicherry.

Studies conducted locally in Pakistan support these international conclusions. According to research by Zeb et al. (2022), one of the main causes of university students' self-medication is poverty. Due to a lack of access to reasonably priced healthcare facilities and cultural norms that value independence, self-medication has become commonplace in underprivileged areas.

People with lower incomes are more at risk for health problems from self-medication. Drug resistance, organ damage, and a delayed diagnosis of critical illnesses are just a few of the catastrophic outcomes that can result from improper drug usage, wrong dosages, and a lack of medical monitoring (Bennadi, 2013). According to Pan et al. (2012), people who self-medicate frequently

don't know how to use drugs properly, which raises the risk of negative side effects.

Additionally, poverty restricts access to health literacy, which makes it more difficult to utilize pharmaceuticals responsibly. According to studies by Hughes et al. (2021), people living in poverty are more likely to be exposed to the risks of self-medication because they are less likely to receive instruction on safe medication practices

Research Gaps

Although there is prosperity of research on self-medication and its socioeconomic causes, there are few local studies examining the particular effects of poverty on university students' self-medication practices. There is a knowledge gap on the particular difficulties experienced by students in resource-constrained environments, such as the University of Swat, because the majority of the research currently in publication concentrates on larger populations. By examining the impact of financial difficulties on university students' self-medication, this study seeks to close this gap.

Methodology

The quantitative research design used in this study is based on positivist philosophy, which prioritizes statistical analysis and objective observation (Collins, 2018). The method guarantees a thorough, methodical examination of how poverty and demographic variables affect University of Swat BS students' self-medication habits. Because of this methodology, hypotheses may be precisely measured and tested using numerical data analysis, which supports the findings' dependability and generalizability (Abawi, 2008). The study's focus is on the 5,001 BS students at the main campus of the University of Swat, which includes 24 departments and 4,098 male and 903 female students (University of Swat Administrative Offices, 2024). A stratified random selection technique was used to choose the sample, guaranteeing that there was a proportionate representation of male and female students in the population. For balanced representation across demographic subgroups, this approach works very well (Bhattacharjee, 2012; Oribhabor & Anyanwu, 2019).

The sample size, which was designed to proportionately reflect the population's strata, was 367 students (300 males and 67 females) using the proportional allocation method (Bougie & Sekaran, 2019). The following formula was used to determine proportional allocation:

$$n_i = n \cdot N_i / N$$

n_i = Sample size for stratum

n = Total sample size

N_i = Population size for stratum

N = Total population size

Putting the values, we got

Male: $n_i = (367/5001) * 4098 = 300.03$ so round down to 300

Female; $n_i = (367/5001) * 903 = 66.97$ so round up to 67

So, the sample sizes for each stratum would be:

Male: 300

Female: 67

Total sample size: 300 + 67 = 367

Data collection tools

Using a standardized questionnaire intended to capture both demographic and poverty characteristics, data was gathered. The following are important variables: Aspects related to demographics: Age, gender, semester, family structure, residential area, Faculties. Poverty level is other variable. The chosen sample was given the questionnaire, and their answers were noted for additional statistical examination. This main technique of gathering data guarantees that the

Demographics variables

Table 1: Residential area of the Respondents

Residential area	Frequency	Percentage
Urban	190	51.8
Rural	177	48.2

Explanation

Table 1 displays According to the survey, self-medication was somewhat more common among urban students (51.8%) than among rural students (48.2%). This is in line with earlier studies conducted in Western India, which found that easy access to pharmacies and lifestyle

information is accurate and pertinent to the goals of the study (Ajayi, 2017). The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the data. There were two main methods used: Characteristic Statistics: to provide an overview of the variables and their distributions by summarizing and presenting data in tabular formats.

Model of Binary Logistic Regression: According to Hosmer, Lemeshow, and Sturdivant (2013), this model is especially well-suited for examining the association between several independent variables and a binary dependent variable (self-medication: yes/no). The following is the general logistic regression equation: $\text{Logit} [\pi(x)] = \ln(1 - \pi(x)) / \pi(x) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x$

To evaluate the probability of self-medication practices under different independent variable situations, odds ratios were computed (Menard, 2002).

Analysis

The next points provide a detailed analysis and interpretation of the results using the Logistic Regression Model and frequency distribution.

Frequency Distribution

The frequency distribution covers the results concerning the demographic profile of the study respondents and the rest of the questions based on the study objectives. A detailed description of the results regarding the basic information and other questions revealed in the questionnaire is below.

characteristics led to increased rates of self-medication among urban residents (Limaye et al., 2018). According to a study conducted in Islamabad, Pakistan, the prevalence of self-medication was 50.6% in rural regions and 64.2% in urban areas (Khan et al., 2022).

Table 2: Age of the Study Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-20	190	51.8
21-23	80	21.8
24 - 26	97	26.4
27 or above	0	0
Total	367	100.0

Explanation:

Table 2 describe the majority of respondents were between 18-20 years (51.8%), followed by 24-26 years (26.4%). Studies indicate that self-medication is more common among younger

individuals. For example, a research in Nepal found that 64.8% of medical students aged 18-25 engaged in self-medication due to perceived understanding about drugs (Gyawali et al., 2015).

Table 3: Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	300	81.7
Female	67	18.3
Total	367	100.0

Explanation:

Table 3 highlights Males were 88% more likely than females to self-medicate, according to this study ($p = 0.02$). However, a study conducted in India found that because of their limited access to healthcare and home duties, women were twice as likely as men to self-medicate (Joshi & Chandra,

2023). The results of the current study, however, are consistent with another study conducted in Lahore, Pakistan, which found that 67.9% of students who self-medicated were male (Ali et al., 2020).

Table 4: Faculty of the Study Respondents

Faculty	Frequency	Percent
Management and Social Sciences	80	21.8
Chemical Silences	20	5.4
Life Sciences	30	8.2
Physical & Numerical Sciences	60	16.3
Religious and Legal Studies	80	21.8
Languages and Literature	97	26.4
Total	367	100.0

Explanation:

Table 4 stratification of the study participants by faculty is shows. According to the findings, 367 students from 06 different faculties took part in the study. The distribution is seeing below. With

97 respondents or 26.4% of the sample, Languages and Literature had the largest presence. With 80 responders each, Management and Social Sciences accounted for 21.8% of the sample, while

Religious and Legal Studies each got 80 respondents. Following with 60 responses, or 16.3% of the total, were the physical and numerical sciences. Thirty respondents, or 8.2% of the total, were from the life sciences sector.

With 20 responders, Chemical Sciences had the lowest representation (5.4% of the sample). non-medical students were more likely to self-medicate due to lack awareness (Zeb et al., 2022).

Table 5. Family structure of the respondents

Family structure	Frequency	Percentage
Nuclear	190	51.8
Joint	80	21.8
Extend	97	26.4
Single parents	0	0
Total	367	100.0

Explanation

The table 5 displays the respondents' family structure, which shows a wide range among the four groups: nuclear, joint, extended, and single parents. Interestingly, nuclear families make up the bulk of responders (51.8%), with 190 people in total. With 80 responders, joint families comprise 21.8% of the sample. Out of the 97 responders, 26.4% are members of extended families. It's interesting to note that no respondents came from single-parent families,

suggesting that this family type is completely absent from the sample. Students from joint families were 42% more likely to self-medicate than those from nuclear families, and those from extended families were 67% more likely. People from nuclear families were more likely to self-medicate (66.9%) than people from extended families (55.9%), according to a study conducted in Faisalabad, Pakistan (Malik & Bhattacharyya, 2019).

Institute for Excellence in Education & Research

Table 6: Semester of the Respondents

Semester	Frequency	Percent
2 nd Semester	120	32.7
4 th Semester	70	19.1
6 th Semester	90	24.5
8 th Semester	87	23.7
10 th Semester	0	0
Total	367	100.0

Explanation:

In Table 06, the distribution of study participants by semester is shown, indicating that the 367 students in the sample represented a variety of academic levels. The following is the break: With 120 responses, or 32.7% of the sample, the 2nd Semester had the largest representation. Ninety responders, or 24.5% of the total, came from the sixth semester. 87 responders, or 23.7% of the participants, are from the eighth semester. Seventy

responders, or 19.1% of the sample, are from the fourth semester. Interestingly, there are no responders for the tenth semester, making up 0% of the total. According to studies conducted in India, senior students' acquaintance with medications and academic stress made them more inclined to self-medicate (Bennadi, 2013).

Table 7: Have you ever taken medicine/drugs without a prescription from a doctor?

Response Category	Frequency	Percent
Yes	321	87.5
No	46	12.5
Total	367	100.0

Explanation:

Table 7 shows The percentage of respondents who used drugs for non-prescription or other purposes is. Of all sampled respondents, 367 (100%) reported taking medications without a prescription, 321 (87.5%) reported doing so, and 46 (12.5%) reported never using drugs without a prescription. According to this study, 87.5% of

students had at least one instance of self-medication. A cross-sectional study conducted in Sokoto, Nigeria, revealed similar proportions, with 51.1% of participants reporting self-medicating two to four times in the previous three months (Ahmed et al., 2023).

Poverty

Table 8: Do you self-medicate because you cannot afford healthcare services?

Response Category	Frequency	Percent
Agree	200	54.5
Strongly agree	50	13.6
Disagree	45	12.3
Strongly disagree	7	1.9
Neutral	55	15.0
Total	367	100.0

Institute for Excellence in Education & Research

Explanation

Table 8 shows that most people (54.5%) agree and 13.6% strongly agree that their self-medication is influenced by financial constraints. Nonetheless, fewer respondents did not consider cost to be a significant factor when deciding to self-medicate, as seen by the 12.3% who disagreed and 1.9% who strongly disagreed. On the other hand, 15.0% had no opinion, which suggests that they don't know

enough about or care about the topic. These findings demonstrate the significance of financial limitations in influencing respondents' inclination to self-medicate. This is in line with studies conducted in Sudan, where the high expense of medical care was a primary cause of poverty and self-medication (Awad et al., 2005).

Table 9: Do you self-medicate to save money?

Response Category	Frequency	Percent
Agree	100	27.3
Strongly agree	150	40.9
Disagree	45	12.3
Strongly disagree	7	1.9
Neutral	55	15.0
Total	367	100.0

Explanation

Table 9 indicates the respondent's impression of self-medication as a strategy to save money. Of the total sampled replies, 367 (100%), 250 (68.2%), 150 (40.9%), 100 (27.3%), 45 (12.3%), 7 (1.9%), and 55 (15.0%) disagreed with the statement that

they self-medicate to save money. Economic motivations were among the most common, with low-income groups exhibiting the highest prevalence, according to a meta-analysis of self-medication habits (Ahmed et al., 2023).

Table 10: Does your financial situation affect your ability to care for your health and well-being?

Response Category	Frequency	Percent
Agree	180	49.0
Strongly agree	20	5.5
Disagree	35	9.5
Strongly disagree	17	4.6
Neutral	55	15.0
Total	367	100.0

Explanation

Table 10 shows the respondents' perceptions of how their financial condition affects their ability to care for their health and well. Out of all the sampled respondents, 367 (100%), 300 (81.7%) agreed, with 120 (32.7%) strongly agreeing, 180 (40.0%) agreeing, 35 (9.5%) disagreeing, 17 (4.6%) strongly disagreeing, and 55 (15.0%) remaining neutral on the statement that their

financial situation affects their ability to take care of their health and well-being. Studies conducted in India and Pakistan have repeatedly demonstrated that people are compelled by financial limitations to look for less expensive options, such as self-medication (Panda et al., 2017).

Table 11: Have you ever self-medicated due to a lack of money for prescription medication?

Response Category	Frequency	Percent
Agree	220	59.0
Strongly agree	30	8.2
Disagree	45	12.3
Strongly disagree	7	1.9
Neutral	55	15.0
Total	367	100.0

Explanation

Table 11 shows the experiences of those who self-medicate because of budgetary constraints. The statement that they had self-medicated because they did not have the money for prescription medication was accepted by 367 (100%) of the sampled respondents, 250 (68.2%), 30 (8.2%) strongly agreeing, 220 (59.0%) agreeing, 45

(12.3%) disagreeing, 07 (1.9%) strongly disagreeing, and 55 (15.0%) remaining neutral. According to Selvaraj et al. (2014), a similar pattern was noted in Pondicherry, India, where those with lower incomes were twice as likely to self-medicate as those with higher incomes.

Table 12: Have you ever used alternative remedies because you could not afford proper medication?

Response Category	Frequency	Percent
Agree	250	68.1
Strongly agree	35	9.5
Disagree	15	4.1
Strongly disagree	7	1.9
Neutral	40	10.9
Total	367	100.0

Explanation

Table 12 shows 367 (100%) of the sampled respondents agreed that they had used alternative therapies because they were unable to afford appropriate medication; 285 (77.5%) agreed, with 35 (9.5%) strongly agreeing, 250 (68.1%) agreeing, 15 (4.1%) disagreeing, 7 (1.9%) strongly

disagreeing, and 40 (10.9%) remaining neutral. According to a study conducted in Eritrea, 77.5% of participants used traditional medicine when access to contemporary treatment was prohibitively expensive (Tesfamariam et al., 2019).

Table 13: Is poverty a driving factor for self-medication in your community

Response Category	Frequency	Percent
Agree	100	27.3
Strongly agree	105	28.6
Disagree	45	12.3
Strongly disagree	7	1.9
Neutral	105	28.6
Total	367	100.0

Table 13 shows that 100 (27.3%) of the respondents believed that poverty is the reason why self-medication is so common in their town. 28.6% strongly agree: Out of the 105 respondents, 105 are adamant that poverty is the main factor causing self-medication in their neighborhood. 12.3% disagree, believing that neighborhood poverty is not the primary reason for self-medication. Disagree strongly (1.9%): Seven respondents vehemently disagree that the primary

reason of self-medication in their neighborhood is poverty. Regarding the topic of whether neighborhood poverty contributes to self-medication usage, 105 respondents (28.6%) are unsure or unconvinced. According to studies conducted in Pakistan, the cost and lack of access to healthcare are the primary reasons why self-medication rates are greater in low-income communities (Malik & Bhattacharyya, 2019).

Table: 14. Do you self-medicate to avoid medical expenses?

Response Category	Frequency	Percent
Agree	105	28.6
Strongly agree	100	27.3
Disagree	105	28.6
Strongly disagree	7	1.9
Neutral	45	12.3
Total	367	100.0

Explanation

Table 14 reveals that 105 respondents (28.6%) + 100 respondents (27.3%) agree or strongly agree that they self-medicate to reduce medical bills, while 105 respondents (28.5%) disagree or strongly disagree, and 12.3% of the total are

neutral. Self-medication was prevalent among students attempting to avoid expensive medical appointments, according to research conducted in Western India (Limaye et al., 2018).

Table 15: Have you ever self-medicated due to a lack of access to low-cost healthcare?

Response Category	Frequency	Percent
Agree	105	28.6
Strongly agree	100	27.3
Disagree	45	12.3
Strongly disagree	7	1.9
Neutral	105	28.6
Total	367	100.0

Explanation

Table 15 highlights the answers provided by participants when asked if they have self-medicated due to a lack of access to reasonably priced healthcare. 105 respondents, or 28.6% of the 367 total, agreed with the statement, indicating that a sizable portion of respondents attribute this element to self-medication. The apparent connection between self-medication and healthcare affordability was further highlighted by the 27.3% (100 respondents) who strongly agreed, 12.3% (45 respondents) disagreed, indicating that for them, self-medication may not be primarily motivated by a lack of affordable healthcare. There was little pushback to the idea, as seen by the 1.9% (7 respondents) who strongly disapproved. 105 respondents, or 28.6%, expressed no opinion,

suggesting indecision or other influencing variables that the statement did not take into consideration. According to a Northern Indian study, one of the main causes of rural communities' self-medication is a lack of healthcare infrastructure (Joshi & Chandra, 2023).

Logistic Regression Model

This section covers the detailed analysis and interpretation of the demographic and main variables of the study influencing self-medication practices among the studied population in a comprehensive database.

Table of binary logistic regression model

Variables	Categories	Odd ratio	Std. Error	Z value	Pr(> z)
Gender	Female	Ref			
	Male	1.88	0.63	2.33	0.02
Age	18-20	Ref			
	21-23	0.96	0.24	0.17	0.87
	24-26	1.03	0.25	0.12	0.90
Faculties	Management and Social Sciences	Ref			
	Physical and Numerical Sciences	1.13	0.26	0.53	0.60
	Chemical Sciences	0.81	0.34	0.53	0.60
	Life Sciences	0.86	0.29	-0.48	0.63
	Religious and Legal Studies	0.92	0.25	-0.31	0.76
	Languages and Literature	1.34	0.22	1.53	0.13
Semester	2	Ref			
	4	0.99	0.23	-0.04	0.97
	6	1.02	0.24	0.08	0.94
	8	1.03	0.25	0.12	0.90
Family structure	Nuclear	Ref			
	Joint	1.42	0.20	2.03	0.04
	Extended	1.67	0.23	2.73	0.01
	Single parent	0.44	0.41	-1.03	0.30
Residential area	Rural	Ref			
	Urban	1.51	0.22	1.90	0.06
Poverty	Low	Ref			
	High	2.29	0.25	4.23	< 0.01

Results

The binary logistic regression model's findings indicate a number of important determinants of students' self-medication. One significant component is gender, male are 88% more likely than female to self-medicate are, statistically significant differences are ($p = 0.02$). This suggests that self-medication practices are more likely to occur in male.

Family structure is also very important. Compared to students from nuclear families, those from extended families are 67% more likely to self-medicate, and those from joint families are 42% more likely. Both results have p-values of 0.04 and 0.01 respectively, indicating statistical significance. On the other hand, although this difference is not

statistically significant ($p = 0.30$), students from single-parent households are 56% less likely to self-medicate than nuclear families. These results demonstrate how family dynamics affect the use of self-medication.

Among the model's predictors, poverty is the most powerful. It is highly statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) that students from high-poverty backgrounds are 129% more likely to self-medicate than from low-poverty households. This emphasizes how socioeconomic considerations have a significant influence on health practices.

Furthermore, students who live in cities are 51% more likely than those who live in rural regions to

self-medicate; this difference is only marginally significant ($p = 0.06$).

There are no discernible effects of other factors on self-medication, including age, faculty, or semester progression. Age groups, faculty types, and semesters all had somewhat different odds of self-medication, but these differences are not statistically significant, suggesting that these characteristics are not as important in predicting self-medication practices in this study. Overall, the analysis shows how gender, family structure, poverty, and residential area have a big impact on students' self-medication.

Discussion

Building upon the research reviewed in this study, the binary logistic regression model identifies important factors that influence self-medication. A crucial factor that is not specifically covered in the referenced literature is revealed by the conclusion that men are 88% more likely than women to self-medicate are ($p = 0.02$). Studies like Shamsi and Bayati (2010) and Hughes et al. (2019) and (Ali et al., 2020). give a broad picture of self-medication, but they do not look at developments that are specific to one gender. This study fills this knowledge gap by indicating that gender is a significant factor in self-medication behaviors.

Students from joint families are 42% more likely to self-medicate than students from nuclear families, while students from extended families are 67% more likely to do so. These notable impacts of family structure are consistent with the social and cultural variables covered in Zeb et al. (2022). , similarly found that individuals from **nuclear families (66.9%)** had higher self-medication rates than those from extended families (55.9%) (Malik & Bhattacharyya, 2019). However, this work is the first to quantify the role of family kinds, a topic that has not been thoroughly examined in earlier research, such as Panda et al. (2017). Further highlighting the complex impact of family dynamics on health behaviors is the finding that students from single-parent households are 56% less likely to self-medicate (not statistically significant).

Poverty was found to be the most important predictor of self-medication, with students from high-poverty homes 129% more likely to self-

medicate ($p < 0.01$), in line with Borges et al. (2019) and Ahmed et al. (2023). Given that people from low-income groups favor less expensive alternatives to professional healthcare, this study supports the idea that financial limitations play a significant role in the prevalence of self-medication. In a similar vein, Selvaraj et al. (2014), who ascribe greater rates of self-medication in urban regions to easier access to over-the-counter medications, concur with the finding that urban students are 51% more likely than rural students to self-medicate ($p = 0.06$). This is consistent with other research in Western India that revealed that urban dwellers' rates of self-medication were higher due to lifestyle factors and easy access to pharmacies (Limaye et al., 2018). A study carried out in Islamabad, Pakistan, found that 64.2% of people in urban areas and 50.6% of those in rural areas self-medicated (Khan et al., 2022). This stands in contrast to Awad et al. (2005), who highlight the disparities in local contexts by emphasizing the reliance on self-medication in rural areas due to restricted healthcare access.

The results of Green et al. (2021), which give socioeconomic considerations precedence over demographic variables in predicting self-medication practices, are supported by the lack of statistically significant effects for age, faculty, and semester progression. This emphasizes even more how little of an impact these traits had on this study. Overall, the results address gaps in gender dynamics and family structure while being consistent with a large portion of the body of previous work. The study adds significant insights to the corpus of knowledge by concentrating on these understudied areas and offering a detailed view of the factors that influence self-medication among University of Swat students.

Conclusion

Key variables of self-medication among University of Swat students are highlighted by the binary logistic regression model, which emphasizes the importance of gender, family structure, poverty, and residential location. Gendered health behaviors are highlighted by the fact that male students are 88% more likely than female students to self-medicate ($p = 0.02$). Another important factor is family structure: kids from joint and

extended families are 42% and 67% more likely to self-medicate, respectively, than students from nuclear households ($p = 0.01$ and $p = 0.04$, respectively). This conclusion is not statistically significant ($p = 0.30$), but students from single-parent households are 56% less likely to self-medicate. The greatest predictor is poverty, with students from high-poor homes showing the largest correlation.

Demonstrating the impact of socioeconomic status on health behaviors, as they were 129% more likely to self-medicate ($p < 0.01$). Living in an urban region somewhat raises the chance of self-medication by 51% when compared to rural areas ($p = 0.06$). There are no discernible effects from other variables, such as age, faculty, or semester progression, indicating their limited utility in predicting self-medication. All things considered, the results highlight how socioeconomic and demographic variables influence students' self-medication habits.

Recommendations

Monitoring Local Pharmacists

To make sure pharmacies do not sell prescription medications without a authentic doctor's prescription, regulatory control should be strengthened.

Implement training programs for pharmacists to inform them about the dangers of self-medication and proper dispensing techniques.

Raising Awareness on the Dangers of Self-Medication

Organize health awareness campaigns at community centers and universities that highlight the dangers of self-medication, including drug resistance, improper dosage, and treatment failure.

Teach students about appropriate medicine usage through campus events, posters, and social media.

Prioritizing Health & Self-Care (Give Time to Your Health)

When students are feeling ill, advise them to consult a doctor rather than immediately self-medicating.

To lessen dependency on needless medications, encourage a healthy lifestyle that includes stress management, exercise, and a balanced diet.

Strengthening Government Laws against Over-the-Counter (OTC) Drug Misuse

Push for stronger pharmaceutical laws to restrict the sale of over-the-counter medications, especially pain relievers and antibiotics.

Pharmacies who offer banned medications without a prescription face severe fines and penalties.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, I., King, R., Akter, S., Akter, R., & Aggarwal, V. R. (2023). Determinants of antibiotic self-medication: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy*, 19(7), 1007-1017.
- Ali, M., Qureshi, A. R., & Zafar, H. (2020). A cross-sectional assessment of self-medication among university students of Lahore, Pakistan. *International Journal of Public Health Research*, 9(3), 112-119.
- Amani, F., Mohammadi, S., Shaker, A., & Shahbazzadegan, S. (2011). Study of arbitrary drug use among students in universities of Ardabil city in 2010. *Journal of Ardabil University of Medical Sciences*, 11(3), 201-207.
- Awad, A., Eltayeb, I., Matowe, L., & Thalib, L. (2005). Self-medication with antibiotics and antimalarials in the community of Khartoum State, Sudan. *J Pharm Pharm Sci*, 8(2), 326-331
- Bennadi, D. (2013). Self-medication: A current challenge. *Journal of basic and clinical pharmacy*, 5(1), 19.
- Borges, R. S., Ortiz, B. L. S., Pereira, A. C. M., Keita, H., & Carvalho, J. C. T. (2019). Rosmarinus officinalis essential oil: A review of its phytochemistry, anti-inflammatory activity, and mechanisms of action involved. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 229, 29-45.

- Fuentes Albarrán, K., & Villa Zapata, L. (2008). Analysis and quantification of self-medication patterns of customers in community pharmacies in southern Chile. *Pharmacy world & science*, 30, 863-868
- Gyawali, S., Shankar, P. R., Poudel, P. P., & Saha, A. (2015). Knowledge, attitude, and practice of self-medication among basic science undergraduate medical students in a medical school in western Nepal. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research: JCDR*, 9(12), FC17.
- Hughes, K., Ford, K., Bellis, M. A., Glendinning, F., Harrison, E., & Passmore, J. (2021). Health and financial costs of adverse childhood experiences in 28 European countries: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet Public Health*, 6(11), e848-e857.
- Joshi, H., & Chandra, R. (2023). Gender differences in self-medication practices: A study in Northern India. *Journal of Public Health Research*, 12(2), 78-86.
- Limaye, A. P., Stapleton, R. D., Peng, L., Gunn, S. R., Kimball, L. E., Hyzy, R., ... & Boeckh, M. (2017). Effect of ganciclovir on IL-6 levels among cytomegalovirus-seropositive adults with critical illness: a randomized clinical trial. *Jama*, 318(8), 731-740.
- Limaye, D., Limaye, V., Fortwengel, G., & Krause, G. (2018). Self-medication practices in urban and rural areas of western India: a cross sectional study. *International Journal of community Medicine and public Health*, 2018(5 (7)), 2672-2685.
- Malik, B., & Bhattacharyya, S. (2019). Antibiotic drug-resistance as a complex system driven by socio-economic growth and antibiotic misuse. *Scientific reports*, 9(1), 9788
- Morgan, V. A., Waterreus, A., Jablensky, A., Mackinnon, A., McGrath, J. J., Carr, V., ... & Saw, S. (2011). People living with psychotic illness 2010. *Canberra: Australian Government*.
- Pan, W., Gibb, A. G., & Dainty, A. R. (2012). Strategies for integrating the use of off-site production technologies in house building. *Journal of construction engineering and management*, 138(11), 1331-1340.
- Panda, A., Pradhan, S., Mohapatro, G., & Kshatri, J. S. (2017). Predictors of over-the-counter medication: A cross-sectional Indian study. *Perspectives in Clinical Research*, 8(2), 79-84. (table 10)
- Rathod, P., Sharma, S., Ukey, U., Sonpimpale, B., Ughade, S., Narlawar, U., ... & Gaikwad Jr, S. D. (2023). Prevalence, pattern, and reasons for self-medication: a community-based cross-sectional study from central India. *Cureus*, 15(1).
- Selvaraj, K., Kumar, S. G., & Ramalingam, A. (2014). Prevalence of self-medication practices and its associated factors in Urban Puducherry, India. *Perspectives in clinical research*, 5(1), 32-36
- Shaghaghi, A., Asadi, M., & Allahverdipour, H. (2014). Predictors of self-medication behavior: a systematic review. *Iranian journal of public health*, 43(2), 136.
- Shamsi, M. O. H. S. E. N., Bayati, A. K. R. A. M., Mohamadbeygi, A., & Tajik, R. (2010). The effect of an educational program based on the *Health Belief Model (HBM)* on preventive behavior of self-medication in women with pregnancy in Arak, Iran.
- Tesfamariam, S., Anand, I. S., Kaleab, G., Berhane, S., Woldai, B., Habte, E., & Russom, M. (2019). Self-medication with over-the-counter drugs, the prevalence of risky practice and its associated factors in pharmacy outlets of Asmara, Eritrea. *BMC Public Health*, 19, 1-9.
- World Health Organization. (2000). Guidelines for the regulatory assessment of medicinal products for use in self-medication. *World health organization*
- Zeb, S., Mushtaq, M., Ahmad, M., Saleem, W., Rabaan, A. A., Naqvi, B. S. Z., ... & Ahmed, N. (2022). Self-medication as an important risk factor for antibiotic resistance: a multi-institutional survey among students. *Antibiotics*, 11(7), 842.